

Human Rights Violations During Armed Conflicts: Legal Protections and International Responses

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Abstract

Armed conflicts are often accompanied by widespread violations of human rights, affecting both military personnel and civilians. This article investigates the legal frameworks aimed at safeguarding human rights during such conflicts, with particular attention to the relationship between International Humanitarian Law (IHL) and International Human Rights Law (IHRL). It outlines key international agreements and conventions that aim to prevent and address abuses and explores mechanisms designed to hold perpetrators accountable. Through case studies of recent conflicts, the article sheds light on the difficulties encountered in enforcing these protections and the role played by international judicial bodies, humanitarian missions, and non-governmental organizations. Additionally, the article reflects on the growing complexities of modern armed conflicts and the challenges they pose to existing legal protections, emphasizing the need for more robust international efforts to uphold human rights.

Keywords:

Human Rights, Armed Conflicts, International Humanitarian Law, International Responses, NGOs, Accountability

Introduction

Human rights violations during armed conflicts have long been a significant issue in both international and non-international conflicts. Despite advances in international law, these violations—often directed at civilians—continue to challenge global peace and security. In conflict zones, there is frequently a breakdown in governance, leading to widespread atrocities such as unlawful killings, torture, sexual violence, and mass displacement. As noted by the International Committee of the Red Cross (ICRC), these violations undermine the core principles of humanity that international humanitarian law seeks to protect¹. Though numerous international treaties exist to limit the effects of war, enforcing these protections is often challenging due to the complexity of modern warfare, non-state actors, and a lack of political will from powerful states².

To fully comprehend the mechanisms designed to safeguard human rights in conflict zones, it is essential to explore the intersection of International Humanitarian Law (IHL) and International Human Rights Law (IHRL). The role of international organizations, such as the United Nations and the International Criminal Court (ICC), as well as non-governmental organizations (NGOs), is crucial in ensuring compliance with these legal frameworks.

Overview of Human Rights Violations in Armed Conflicts

Human rights violations in the context of armed conflicts are among the most severe crimes under international law. As highlighted by the Geneva Conventions of 1949, these violations encompass actions such as the targeting of civilians, indiscriminate attacks, enforced disappearances, and inhumane treatment of prisoners of war³. A key principle of International Humanitarian Law is the "distinction" between combatants and civilians, yet this principle is frequently ignored by warring factions.

¹ International Committee of the Red Cross (ICRC), *International Humanitarian Law and the Challenges of Contemporary Armed Conflicts* (ICRC Report, 2015)

² *Ibid.*

³ Geneva Conventions, 1949, common Article 3.

In particular, sexual violence has become an increasingly widespread violation, disproportionately affecting women and children. The United Nations Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights (OHCHR) has documented the use of sexual violence as a weapon of war in many recent conflicts, aimed at terrorizing and displacing populations⁴. The impact of such violence extends beyond the immediate victims, contributing to the destabilization of entire communities. Additionally, forced displacement caused by armed conflicts has resulted in unprecedented levels of migration, with millions of individuals fleeing violence, as reported by the UNHCR⁵.

Torture, extrajudicial killings, and illegal detentions are also commonly reported in modern conflict zones. These acts violate both IHL and IHRL, but accountability remains inconsistent. Though international bodies like the ICC are tasked with prosecuting such crimes, the political and logistical challenges involved often delay justice. As the ICC itself has acknowledged, jurisdictional limitations and political resistance by certain states have hindered the prosecution of war criminals⁶.

Legal Protections Under International Humanitarian Law (IHL)

International Humanitarian Law (IHL) is the body of law that governs the conduct of armed conflicts and seeks to limit its effects, primarily by protecting those who are not or no longer participating in hostilities. The most well-known sources of IHL are the Geneva Conventions of 1949 and their Additional Protocols, which form the cornerstone of protections during armed conflicts⁷. The Geneva Conventions set out comprehensive legal protections for civilians, medical personnel, and prisoners of war, among others, aiming to ensure humane treatment and minimize suffering even amidst conflict.

⁴ United Nations Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights (OHCHR), *Sexual Violence in Conflict: New Dimensions of Violence* (OHCHR Report, 2020).

⁵ United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR), *Global Trends: Forced Displacement in 2021* (UNHCR Report, 2022).

⁶ International Criminal Court (ICC), *The Challenges of Prosecution in Contemporary Conflicts* (ICC Report, 2018).

⁷ Geneva Conventions, 1949.

One of the central principles of IHL is the concept of "distinction," which requires belligerents to differentiate between combatants and non-combatants at all times. The targeting of civilians, as stipulated by the Geneva Conventions, is strictly prohibited and constitutes a war crime⁸. IHL also mandates the proportionality of attacks, meaning that military actions must not result in excessive harm to civilians compared to the anticipated military advantage.

A critical aspect of IHL is its application to both international and non-international armed conflicts, although the legal protections may vary slightly between these two types of warfare. In non-international conflicts, common Article 3 of the Geneva Conventions offers basic protections, prohibiting acts such as murder, torture, and cruel treatment of persons not actively involved in hostilities⁹. While these rules provide a legal framework, enforcement remains a challenge. The International Committee of the Red Cross (ICRC) plays a vital role in monitoring compliance with IHL, although it often faces significant obstacles in conflict zones due to access restrictions and the non-cooperation of warring parties¹⁰.

Role of International Human Rights Law (IHRL) in Armed Conflicts

International Human Rights Law (IHRL) complements International Humanitarian Law by providing a broader framework for the protection of individual rights, even in times of conflict. While IHL is specific to wartime, IHRL is applicable both in peacetime and during armed conflicts, creating a dual system of protection¹¹. Core international human rights instruments, such as the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR) and the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR), emphasize the

⁸ *Ibid.*, Additional Protocol I, Article 51(2).

⁹ *Ibid.*, common Article 3.

¹⁰ International Committee of the Red Cross (ICRC), *The Role of the ICRC in Enforcing International Humanitarian Law*, 2020.

¹¹ United Nations Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights (OHCHR), *International Human Rights Law and International Humanitarian Law: Compatibility and Complementarity*, 2011.

protection of fundamental rights, such as the right to life, the prohibition of torture, and the right to a fair trial¹².

In situations of armed conflict, IHRL continues to apply, although certain rights may be lawfully suspended in emergency situations, provided such derogations are strictly necessary and proportional to the situation at hand¹³. However, there are non-derogable rights, such as the right to life (except in lawful acts of war) and the prohibition of torture, that must be upheld at all times. This overlap between IHRL and IHL is often critical in ensuring broader protections, particularly in conflicts involving non-state actors who may not be bound by traditional IHL obligations.

The role of international human rights bodies, such as the United Nations Human Rights Council (UNHRC), becomes pivotal in ensuring that human rights violations are investigated and addressed, even during armed conflicts. The UNHRC often conducts fact-finding missions to document human rights abuses and make recommendations for accountability¹⁴. However, like IHL, the enforcement of IHRL in conflict zones is hindered by political complexities, non-state actors, and limited access for international monitors¹⁵.

Key International Treaties and Conventions

A robust framework of international treaties and conventions forms the foundation for the protection of human rights during armed conflicts. Among the most important is the Geneva Conventions of 1949, which establish critical protections for wounded soldiers, prisoners of war, and civilians in both international and non-international armed conflicts¹⁶. The Additional Protocols of 1977 further develop these protections,

¹² International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR), 1966; Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR), 1948.

¹³ Ibid., ICCPR, Article 4.

¹⁴ United Nations Human Rights Council (UNHRC), Report on the Human Rights Situation in Conflict Zones, 2022.

¹⁵ OHCHR, Challenges in Monitoring Human Rights in Armed Conflicts, 2019.

¹⁶ Geneva Conventions, 1949.

particularly with respect to civilian populations and non-international conflicts¹⁷. These treaties are considered the bedrock of International Humanitarian Law (IHL) and have been ratified by almost all states.

Complementing the Geneva Conventions is the Convention Against Torture and Other Cruel, Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment (CAT), which categorically prohibits torture, even during wartime¹⁸. The International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR) and the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR) also serve as key instruments in providing legal protections, particularly through their emphasis on the right to life, prohibition of torture, and fair trial standards¹⁹.

The Rome Statute of the International Criminal Court (ICC) is another essential treaty, as it establishes the ICC's jurisdiction over war crimes, crimes against humanity, and genocide²⁰. This statute plays a critical role in holding individuals accountable for gross violations of human rights and IHL during armed conflicts. Additionally, the Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC) and its Optional Protocols emphasize the protection of children in conflict zones, prohibiting their recruitment into armed forces²¹.

While these treaties provide a robust legal framework, ensuring compliance and enforcement remains a challenge, particularly in modern asymmetric conflicts where non-state actors are heavily involved. States are obligated under international law to adhere to these treaties, but enforcement often requires the cooperation of multiple international and domestic mechanisms.

¹⁷ Geneva Conventions, Additional Protocols, 1977, Articles 48-50.

¹⁸ Convention Against Torture and Other Cruel, Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment (CAT), 1984, Article 2.

¹⁹ International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR), 1966; Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR), 1948.

²⁰ Rome Statute of the International Criminal Court, 1998, Articles 5-8.

²¹ Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC), 1989; Optional Protocol on the Involvement of Children in Armed Conflict, 2000.

Responsibility of States and Non-State Actors

Both states and non-state actors have specific responsibilities under International Humanitarian Law (IHL) and International Human Rights Law (IHRL) during armed conflicts. Under IHL, states have the primary duty to respect and ensure respect for the rules of armed conflict, including protecting civilians, treating prisoners of war humanely, and refraining from indiscriminate attacks²². States are also required to take preventive measures to ensure their military forces comply with IHL, including through training and dissemination of legal principles²³.

Non-state actors, including insurgent groups, militias, and other armed entities, are also bound by the principles of IHL. Common Article 3 of the Geneva Conventions specifically extends protections to non-international armed conflicts, requiring that all parties to a conflict, including non-state actors, refrain from actions such as murder, torture, and cruel treatment²⁴. Despite this, enforcing accountability for non-state actors is significantly more complex, as they may not be signatories to international treaties, nor do they always operate within recognized state borders.

In addition to IHL, both state and non-state actors are subject to International Human Rights Law. While IHRL primarily binds states, non-state actors are increasingly recognized as having human rights responsibilities, particularly when they exercise control over territories or populations²⁵. The United Nations and other international bodies have emphasized the need for non-state actors to adhere to basic human rights norms, especially in conflicts where they act as *de facto* authorities²⁶.

States also bear responsibility for the actions of non-state actors operating within their territories. Under the principle of due diligence, states must prevent, investigate, and

²² Geneva Conventions, 1949, common Article 1.

²³ International Committee of the Red Cross (ICRC), *The Role of States in Ensuring Respect for International Humanitarian Law*, 2016.

²⁴ *Ibid.*, common Article 3.

²⁵ United Nations, *Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights*, 2011.

²⁶ United Nations Security Council, Resolution 2250 on Youth, Peace, and Security, 2015.

punish human rights violations by non-state actors, even if the state itself is not directly involved in the conflict²⁷. The Rome Statute of the ICC further clarifies that both state and non-state actors can be held individually accountable for war crimes and crimes against humanity, reinforcing the shared responsibility to protect human rights in times of conflict²⁸.

International Responses and Enforcement Mechanisms

The international community has developed a variety of responses and enforcement mechanisms to address human rights violations during armed conflicts. These mechanisms aim to hold perpetrators accountable, deter future violations, and provide reparations to victims. The United Nations (UN) plays a central role in coordinating international responses through its peacekeeping missions, sanctions regimes, and diplomatic efforts. UN peacekeeping operations are often deployed in conflict zones to protect civilians, monitor ceasefires, and support the implementation of peace agreements²⁹. Additionally, the UN Security Council (UNSC) has the authority to impose sanctions, including arms embargoes and travel bans, on individuals and entities responsible for serious human rights abuses³⁰.

Humanitarian interventions, though controversial, have also been employed by states and coalitions to prevent or halt mass atrocities. Under the doctrine of Responsibility to Protect (R2P), the international community is obligated to intervene when a state is either unwilling or unable to prevent genocide, war crimes, or crimes against humanity

²⁷ United Nations Human Rights Council, *State Responsibility and the Principle of Due Diligence in Human Rights Law*, 2017.

²⁸ Rome Statute of the International Criminal Court, 1998.

²⁹ United Nations Peacekeeping, *Protecting Civilians: Mandates and Operations*, 2020.

³⁰ United Nations Security Council, *Resolution 1970 on Sanctions Against Libya*, 2011.

within its borders³¹. However, R2P has faced criticism for its selective application and potential misuse as a cover for political or military objectives³².

Another important mechanism is the role of fact-finding missions and international commissions of inquiry, often mandated by the UN Human Rights Council (UNHRC). These bodies investigate alleged human rights violations in conflict zones, gather evidence, and issue reports with recommendations for action. Their findings can be used to pressure states or non-state actors to comply with international law, or to serve as the basis for judicial proceedings in international courts³³.

Non-governmental organizations (NGOs) also play a vital role in documenting abuses, advocating for accountability, and providing humanitarian assistance to victims. Organizations like Human Rights Watch (HRW) and Amnesty International often work alongside international institutions to monitor violations and lobby for stronger enforcement of international norms³⁴.

Role of International Criminal Court (ICC) and Other Judicial Bodies

The International Criminal Court (ICC) is a central institution in the global effort to prosecute individuals responsible for the gravest human rights violations during armed conflicts, including war crimes, crimes against humanity, and genocide. Established by the Rome Statute in 1998, the ICC has jurisdiction over individuals, regardless of their official capacity, who commit these atrocities³⁵. The court operates on the principle of complementarity, meaning it only intervenes when national courts are unwilling or

³¹ United Nations General Assembly, World Summit Outcome Document, 2005, paragraphs 138-139.

³² Bellamy, Alex J., *Responsibility to Protect: A Defense*, Oxford University Press, 2015.

³³ United Nations Human Rights Council, *Fact-Finding Mission on Myanmar: Detailed Findings*, 2018.

³⁴ Amnesty International, *Human Rights Violations in Conflict Zones: Annual Report 2022*, 2022.

³⁵ Rome Statute of the International Criminal Court, 1998, Articles 5-8.

unable to prosecute alleged perpetrators³⁶. By prosecuting war criminals, the ICC aims to deliver justice to victims and act as a deterrent for future crimes.

The ICC has played a critical role in several high-profile cases, such as the prosecution of individuals responsible for crimes in Darfur, the Democratic Republic of Congo, and Uganda³⁷. However, the court faces significant challenges, including political resistance from powerful states that have not ratified the Rome Statute, such as the United States, China, and Russia. This limits its reach and effectiveness in certain conflicts³⁸.

Beyond the ICC, other international and regional judicial bodies contribute to the enforcement of human rights laws during conflicts. The International Court of Justice (ICJ), also known as the World Court, adjudicates disputes between states and has ruled on cases involving breaches of international humanitarian law, such as in the Bosnian Genocide case³⁹. Regional courts, like the European Court of Human Rights (ECHR) and the Inter-American Court of Human Rights, have also delivered landmark rulings on state accountability for human rights violations during conflicts⁴⁰.

These courts, along with hybrid tribunals like the Special Court for Sierra Leone and the Extraordinary Chambers in the Courts of Cambodia, demonstrate the increasing role of international judicial bodies in ensuring accountability. However, the enforcement of judgments remains a major hurdle, as compliance often depends on political will and international pressure.

³⁶ *Ibid.*, Article 17.

³⁷ International Criminal Court, Cases and Situations, 2023.

³⁸ Bosco, David, *Rough Justice: The International Criminal Court in a World of Power Politics*, Oxford University Press, 2014.

³⁹ International Court of Justice, *Application of the Convention on the Prevention and Punishment of the Crime of Genocide (Bosnia and Herzegovina v. Serbia and Montenegro)*, 2007.

⁴⁰ European Court of Human Rights, *Case of Jaloud v. The Netherlands*, 2014; Inter-American Court of Human Rights, *Case of the Mapiripán Massacre v. Colombia*, 2005.

Challenges in Enforcing Human Rights Protections in Conflict Zones

Enforcing human rights protections in conflict zones presents numerous challenges, both legal and practical. One of the primary obstacles is the breakdown of state authority, which often leads to lawlessness and impunity for perpetrators of human rights violations⁴¹. In many conflict zones, governments may be too weak to maintain order, or they may be directly involved in the abuses, making domestic enforcement mechanisms ineffective. This leaves civilians vulnerable to war crimes, forced displacement, and other atrocities.

Another significant challenge is the involvement of non-state actors. Many modern conflicts involve armed groups, insurgencies, and militias that are not formally bound by international treaties, including the Geneva Conventions⁴². While International Humanitarian Law (IHL) applies to these actors, ensuring compliance is far more difficult, as they often lack the organizational structure of state militaries and may disregard international norms altogether. The fluidity of conflict lines and the frequent use of guerrilla tactics further complicate efforts to monitor and enforce human rights protections⁴³.

Additionally, access to conflict zones for international organizations, including the United Nations, non-governmental organizations (NGOs), and fact-finding missions, is often restricted. Warring parties may block humanitarian access, fearing that international oversight could expose their crimes or weaken their strategic positions⁴⁴. This not only hampers efforts to gather evidence but also restricts the delivery of humanitarian aid to affected populations.

⁴¹ Kaldor, Mary, *New and Old Wars: Organized Violence in a Global Era*, Polity Press, 2012.

⁴² International Committee of the Red Cross (ICRC), *International Humanitarian Law and Non-State Actors*, 2019.

⁴³ *Ibid.*

⁴⁴ United Nations Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (OCHA), *Humanitarian Access Overview*, 2021.

Political considerations also play a significant role in undermining enforcement. Powerful states may obstruct international efforts to address violations if their geopolitical interests are at stake. This is particularly evident in the United Nations Security Council (UNSC), where the use of veto power by permanent members can prevent meaningful action against rights violations⁴⁵. Moreover, the lack of political will to prosecute human rights offenders—whether due to alliances with violators or fears of domestic instability—further complicates the enforcement of international laws.

Finally, even when human rights violators are prosecuted, impunity remains a major issue. In many cases, those responsible for grave violations escape justice due to the inability or unwillingness of national courts to carry out prosecutions. International tribunals, like the International Criminal Court (ICC), often face challenges in apprehending suspects, especially when they are protected by powerful states or have strong local support⁴⁶.

Humanitarian Interventions and Peacekeeping Operations

Humanitarian interventions and peacekeeping operations have become essential tools for protecting human rights in conflict zones, though their effectiveness is often debated. Humanitarian intervention refers to the use of force by states or international coalitions to prevent or stop mass atrocities, such as genocide or war crimes, when a government is either perpetrating these crimes or unable to stop them. The principle of Responsibility to Protect (R2P), endorsed by the United Nations in 2005, provides a framework for such interventions, asserting that the international community has an obligation to intervene when a state fails to protect its own people from mass atrocities⁴⁷.

⁴⁵ United Nations Security Council, *Vetoes in the Security Council: A Record of Inaction*, 2023.

⁴⁶ Bosco, David, *Rough Justice: The International Criminal Court in a World of Power Politics*, Oxford University Press, 2014.

⁴⁷ United Nations General Assembly, *World Summit Outcome Document*, 2005, paragraphs 138-139.

Despite the noble intentions behind R2P, humanitarian interventions are fraught with political, ethical, and practical challenges. Critics argue that interventions can be misused as a pretext for political or military objectives, as seen in controversial cases like the NATO intervention in Libya in 2011⁴⁸. Moreover, interventions often face legitimacy issues, particularly when they are carried out without explicit authorization from the United Nations Security Council (UNSC). This has raised concerns about the selective application of R2P and the violation of state sovereignty⁴⁹.

Peacekeeping operations, typically authorized by the UN, aim to maintain or restore peace in conflict zones by deploying international forces to monitor ceasefires, protect civilians, and support the implementation of peace agreements. While UN peacekeeping missions have contributed to stability in various regions, their effectiveness is often hampered by resource limitations and mandate restrictions. Many missions are underfunded, poorly equipped, or limited to monitoring and reporting without the capacity to actively prevent violence⁵⁰. Moreover, peacekeepers sometimes face hostility from local factions, putting them at risk and reducing their ability to fulfill their mandates⁵¹.

Another challenge is the lack of coordination between peacekeeping forces and humanitarian organizations. While both aim to protect civilians, differing objectives and operational constraints can lead to tensions or gaps in protection. Additionally, peacekeeping missions are often dependent on the cooperation of local authorities or warring parties, which can be difficult to secure in the chaotic environment of armed conflicts⁵².

⁴⁸ Bellamy, Alex J., *Responsibility to Protect: A Defense*, Oxford University Press, 2015.

⁴⁹ *Ibid.*

⁵⁰ United Nations Peacekeeping, *Challenges and Opportunities in Peacekeeping Operations*, 2022.

⁵¹ United Nations Security Council, *Report on Attacks Against Peacekeepers*, 2020.

⁵² Amnesty International, *Peacekeeping and Human Rights Protection in Conflict Zones*, 2021.

Despite these challenges, peacekeeping operations have achieved notable successes in reducing violence and supporting post-conflict reconstruction. For instance, UN missions in Sierra Leone and Liberia helped to stabilize these countries following years of civil war, illustrating the potential of peacekeeping efforts when adequately supported and resourced⁵³.

Role of Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs)

Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) play a critical role in addressing human rights violations during armed conflicts by providing humanitarian assistance, advocating for accountability, and raising awareness about abuses. Many NGOs, such as **Human Rights Watch** and **Amnesty International**, focus on monitoring and documenting human rights violations, compiling reports that serve as vital evidence for international bodies and local governments⁵⁴. Their investigative work often brings attention to atrocities that might otherwise go unreported, creating pressure on perpetrators and calling for accountability.

NGOs also engage in **advocacy efforts** aimed at influencing public policy and international responses to human rights violations. They work to mobilize public opinion, lobby governments, and push for stronger legal frameworks to protect human rights during conflicts⁵⁵. Their involvement can lead to significant changes in policy, as they often collaborate with international organizations, such as the **United Nations** and regional bodies, to implement human rights standards and provide technical assistance.

In addition to monitoring and advocacy, NGOs provide essential **humanitarian aid** to affected populations, including food, medical care, and shelter. Organizations like the **International Federation of Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies (IFRC)** and **Doctors Without Borders (MSF)** operate in conflict zones, often in cooperation with

⁵³ United Nations Peacekeeping, *Sierra Leone: A Success Story in Peacekeeping*, 2005.

⁵⁴ Human Rights Watch, *World Report 2022: Events of 2021*, 2022.

⁵⁵ Amnesty International, *Report 2022: The State of the World's Human Rights*, 2022.

international bodies to deliver life-saving assistance⁵⁶. Their work is vital, especially in contexts where state authorities are unable or unwilling to provide support.

Despite their critical contributions, NGOs often face numerous challenges in conflict zones, including **restricted access** due to violence, bureaucratic hurdles, and hostility from armed groups or state actors⁵⁷. Some NGOs may also confront **security threats**, making it difficult for them to operate effectively or safely in certain regions. Furthermore, political considerations can complicate their efforts, as states may perceive NGOs as foreign actors interfering in domestic affairs, leading to accusations of bias or destabilization⁵⁸.

Emerging Issues and Contemporary Challenges in Armed Conflicts

Armed conflicts today are characterized by a range of emerging issues and contemporary challenges that complicate the enforcement of human rights protections. One of the most pressing concerns is the **increasing prevalence of non-state armed groups**, which often operate outside traditional frameworks of accountability and humanitarian norms. These groups may engage in practices such as forced recruitment, sexual violence, and the use of child soldiers, raising urgent questions about the applicability of International Humanitarian Law (IHL) and the enforcement of human rights standards⁵⁹.

Additionally, the **proliferation of modern warfare technologies**, including drones and autonomous weapons systems, poses significant challenges for accountability and ethical considerations. These technologies can make it more difficult to distinguish between combatants and civilians, leading to increased civilian casualties and

⁵⁶ International Federation of Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies (IFRC), World Disasters Report 2021, 2021.

⁵⁷ United Nations Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (OCHA), Humanitarian Access Overview, 2021.

⁵⁸ Murdock, Heather, NGOs in Conflict Zones: Challenges and Opportunities, International Peace Institute, 2019.

⁵⁹ International Committee of the Red Cross (ICRC), *Non-State Armed Groups and International Humanitarian Law*, 2020.

complicating the application of IHL⁶⁰. The use of drones, in particular, raises questions about transparency and oversight, as remote strikes may occur without adequate legal scrutiny or accountability⁶¹.

Another emerging issue is the impact of **climate change on armed conflicts**, which exacerbates resource scarcity, displacement, and competition for natural resources. Environmental degradation can fuel tensions and lead to violence, particularly in regions already vulnerable to conflict⁶². As climate change continues to affect food and water security, it is increasingly recognized as a threat multiplier that can intensify existing conflicts and create new ones.

Gender-based violence remains a critical challenge in armed conflicts, with women and girls disproportionately affected by sexual violence, exploitation, and trafficking. While international legal frameworks, such as **UN Security Council Resolution 1325**, emphasize the importance of protecting women in conflicts, implementation remains inconsistent, and many survivors face stigma and lack of access to justice⁶³.

Finally, the **COVID-19 pandemic** has further complicated the landscape of armed conflicts, as lockdowns and resource shortages limit humanitarian access and exacerbate existing vulnerabilities. The pandemic has strained health systems, disrupted aid delivery, and increased the risks faced by civilians in conflict zones, highlighting the urgent need for a coordinated international response to protect human rights in times of crisis⁶⁴.

⁶⁰ ICRC, *Autonomous Weapons: The Need for a New International Legal Framework*, 2021.

⁶¹ Stanford Law School, *Drone Strikes and International Law*, 2020.

⁶² United Nations Environment Programme, *Climate Change and Armed Conflict*, 2021.

⁶³ United Nations Security Council, *Women, Peace, and Security: The Role of Women in Peacebuilding*, Resolution 1325, 2000.

⁶⁴ United Nations, *COVID-19 and Human Rights: We Are All in This Together*, 2020.

Conclusion

Human rights violations during armed conflicts represent one of the most pressing challenges to global peace and security, requiring a multifaceted approach that integrates legal protections, international responses, and the active involvement of various stakeholders. Despite the existence of robust frameworks under International Humanitarian Law (IHL) and International Human Rights Law (IHRL), the enforcement of these protections remains inadequate in many conflict zones. The role of international treaties and conventions is pivotal; however, challenges such as state sovereignty, political will, and the complexities of non-state actors often undermine their effectiveness.

The responsibility of states and non-state actors to uphold human rights standards during armed conflicts is critical. While the international community has made strides in establishing accountability mechanisms, including the International Criminal Court (ICC), the challenges of jurisdiction, enforcement, and political resistance remain significant. Furthermore, the effectiveness of international responses, including humanitarian interventions and peacekeeping operations, is often hampered by resource constraints, access issues, and the complexities of modern conflicts.

Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) play an essential role in monitoring violations, providing humanitarian aid, and advocating for accountability, but they too face considerable challenges in conflict settings. Emerging issues, such as the impact of climate change on conflict dynamics and the use of new technologies in warfare, further complicate the landscape of human rights protections.

Ultimately, addressing human rights violations in armed conflicts necessitates a comprehensive approach that fosters collaboration among states, international organizations, NGOs, and local communities. By strengthening legal frameworks, enhancing enforcement mechanisms, and prioritizing the protection of civilians, the international community can work toward ensuring that human rights are upheld, even in the most challenging circumstances of armed conflict. Only through sustained commitment and cooperation can we hope to mitigate the suffering of affected populations and promote a future where human rights are respected universally.